

Tetraethylphosphonium Nitrite.

BY PRAFULLA CHANDRA RÂY AND NIRMALENDUNATH RAY.

One of us has described the preparation of ammonium nitrite (Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 345) and also that of alkyl ammonium nitrites (Rây and Rakshit, *ibid.*, 1911, 99, 1017, 1470). In continuation of this work the preparation of tetraethylphosphonium nitrite has been undertaken.

Method of Preparation.—Tetraethylphosphonium iodide* and pure recrystallised silver nitrite were triturated in a mortar in presence of minimum quantity of water, care being taken that in the filtrate there was a slight excess of silver nitrite. The latter was removed by cautious addition of a dilute solution of tetraethylphosphonium iodide until neither of the reacting substances was in excess. It was however found that a considerable quantity of tetraethylphosphonium iodide was lost as it forms an insoluble double salt with silver iodide (cf. Masson and Kirkland, *J. Chem.*

* As considerable quantities of tetraethylphosphonium iodide were required for our present purpose as also for the preparation of tetraethylphosphonium sulphate—a component of a series of double salts with the sulphates of the copper-iron group, a detailed account of the preparation of the parent substance is given below:—

Hofmann's method was naturally tried first (*Annalen*, 1857, 104, 16). Frequent explosions, however, took place during heating phosphonium iodide with ethylalcohol in a sealed tube. This method was, therefore, abandoned in favour of that of Masson and Kirkland (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1889, 58, 138). These chemists had to use a large quantity of silver oxide in view of the fact that a considerable amount of hydriodic acid is formed after reduction of the polyiodides with sulphuretted hydrogen and also that unless an excess of moist silver oxide is used a portion of the tetraethylphosphonium iodide is likely to be lost in the form of an insoluble double halide with silver iodide. They, however, suggest the alternative process in which the aqueous solution of the tetraethylphosphonium iodide containing a large quantity of hydriodic acid is treated with potassium carbonate when the tetraethylphosphonium iodide separates out as an oily layer on the top. The 'oil' is then partly evaporated on the water-bath when crystals begin to appear. It is dried in a desiccator and is then taken up with alcohol and finally precipitated with ether. The product, however, was found to be contaminated with potassium iodide, a fact which seems to have been overlooked by Masson and Kirkland. It had, therefore, to be redissolved in water and again separated from the solution by the addition of potassium carbonate as above. It was often necessary to repeat the process twice or thrice in order to remove the last traces of potassium iodide. The yield however is greatly reduced.

Soc., 1889, 55, 136), a product of the reaction. As the yield of the nitrite was consequently too low, an alternative method was adopted. The tetraethylphosphonium iodide was treated with an excess of silver oxide. The hydroxide thus obtained was neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid. The sulphate of the base was then treated with the requisite amount of pure recrystallised barium nitrite. The tetraethylphosphonium nitrite obtained in solution was filtered and evaporated in a vacuum over sulphuric acid.

Properties.—Tetraethylphosphonium nitrite is a crystalline compound, having a faint yellowish tint, characteristic of the nitrites in general. It is very deliquescent and therefore great care had to be exercised in handling the substance in the atmosphere of the laboratory.

Analysis:—

Found: N, 7.07; P, 16.34; C, 48.25; H, 10.64.

(C₂H₅)₄PNO₂ requires N, 7.25; P, 16.06; C, 49.74; H, 10.44 per cent.

N.B.—Owing to the extremely deliquescent character of the nitrite it has been found very difficult to keep it from absorbing moisture from the atmosphere at the time of weighing and this probably accounts for slightly low results in the estimation of nitrogen.

The phosphorus was estimated by heating the substance in a sealed tube with nitric acid (d 1.5) as in Carius' method for four hours. After opening the tube, the excess of nitric acid was evaporated nearly to dryness and the acid neutralised with sodium carbonate. The mass was then transferred to a platinum crucible and fused with potassium nitrate and sodium carbonate. The filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the phosphorus precipitated with magnesia mixture. It was found that the phosphorus often came out too low. This evidently was due to the fact that a portion of the alkylphosphine escapes oxidation.

The carbon also sometimes comes out even lower. Traces of alkylphosphine, it would appear escape, oxidation, however longer the column of oxide of copper be interposed during combustion and however cautiously the heating be effected.

The physical properties of the tetraethylphosphonium nitrite will form the subject of a subsequent communication.